

THE MECHANICAL EFFECTS OF DENSE UV-RADIATION ON PULTRUDED POLYMER-MATRIX

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1 Introduction

Polymer composites are increasingly used for the rehabilitation of structural systems components in civil engineering. They have also shown promising potential as building materials (including marine works). Their main advantages consist of: their excellent mechanical and corrosion, their advantageous stiffness/mass ratio, good processability and ease of installation. These advantages have led to consider the potential use of the latter replacing the more conventional materials such as steel and reinforced concrete, in some applications.

However, despite these considerable benefits, certain key questions remain about their durability and environmental performance over the long term. Indeed, the external environment can be detrimental: moisture [1], acid rain, thermal fatigue, etc. Parallel to these effects, ultraviolet (UV) radiation exposure can reduce the overall performance of polymers and reinforcing fibers [2] and this is the topic of the work presented.

In this study, samples were exposed in the SPHERE (Simulated Photo-degradation via High Energy Radiant Exposure, NIST, Gaithersburg, MD., USA). The use of nanoindentation allows the characterization of local mechanical properties of these materials. However, to verify the assumption of hydrostatic stress, mirror-type polishing must be fulfilled. However, the highlight of a strong roughness, as a result of UV exposure is a real problem. Mirror-polishing would bypass the rough surface contains all the information, we want to exploit. The challenge of this study is to propose a method of bypassing the problem of roughness, knowing that it is impossible to polish the surface exposed to the risk of eliminating layer to analyze.

2 Materials & Methods

Samples of vinylester, as well as those of composites made by pultrusion (volume fraction of glass fibers of 66% and a vinylester matrix) are cut using a diamond saw and polished with sandpaper 600, 800 and 1200, then solutions with diamond whose grain sizes are respectively 15, 9, 6, 3, 1 and 0.05 microns. To study the cross sections, the samples were cut transversely, polished and coated using the same protocol.

2.1 UV exposure (Simulated Photodegradation via High Energy Radiant Exposure, SPHERE)

Developed at NIST (Gaithersburg, Md, USA), the sphere provides a source of UV radiation of wavelengths between 290 nm to 400 nm [3]. The exposition was carried out under extreme conditions: samples were initially exposed to 55 ° C with a humidity of 75% for about 2 days, then the temperature was decreased to 35 ° C and after 4 days humidity was decreased to 50% and until the end of the trials. The flux received is about 150W / m². A series of samples were removed from the SPHERE after 2 weeks of exposure and a second completed 4 weeks exposure. The third set received no UV exposure and was used as comparison.

2.2 Surface morphology

The surface morphology is characterized by a confocal microscope Zeiss LSM510-type, which can also measure the roughness of the sample. This technique uses a coherent light (HeNe, 543 nm) and collects light exclusively from the focal plane, while rejecting it out of this plane. The images were processed using the software. By moving the focal plane, single images (optical slices) can be combined to build a three-dimensional image.

2.3 Nanoindentation

Unlike the static test of macro and micro hardness, instrumented nanoindentation not only has a very high spatial resolution, but also provides real-time, data of force and penetration when loading and unloading (Fig. 1). When the indenter penetrates the material, elastic and plastic deformations cause the formation of an impression of hardness. When removing the tip, only the elastic part of displacement is recovered. It is this recovery that determines the elastic properties. The contact surface allows to evaluate the hardness [4.6 to 8].

For the following calculations, we limit the discussion to a continuous and isotropic material, whose dimensions are very large compared to the depth of indentation. Surfaces are considered smooth and the contact is frictionless. Furthermore, we assume that there is no time dependence and absence of cracking during indentation (this is confirmed by microscopic observations). Finally, the results can not be exploited if the applied stress is not hydrostatic. Under these conditions, the hardness and Young's modulus can be defined locally by equations 1-2:

$$H = \frac{P}{A} \quad (1)$$

$$E_r = \frac{\sqrt{\pi} S}{\beta \sqrt{A}} \quad (2)$$

Where H is the Hardness, P the load, the contact surface, the reduced modulus, E_r , S is the stiffness, a correction factor β of the point ($\beta = 1$ for a circular contact, $\beta = 1034$ for a Berkovich).

The measurements were performed using the MTS nanoindenter Nanoinstruments, NanoXP. Resolutions load and displacement are 50 nN and 0.04 nm, respectively. Two types of indenters were used to compare and validate the results, whatever the form of indentation: a conical indenter, 10 microns and angle of the cone, 90° , and a pyramidal indenter, Berkovich type. The results are similar but the Berkovich indenter is preferred for better visualization of the indentation under confocal microscopy (Fig. 2). The calibration of the indenter is performed using the known characteristics of fused silica. The loading was performed at a constant strain rate of 0.05 s^{-1} . The depths used for this study are 500, 750 and 1000 nm. To avoid any

interaction between them, the indentations are spaced by at least 50 microns.

Two methods are used to determine the stiffness: the method of unloading, where the stiffness is the slope at the origin of the unloading curve and the Continuous stiffness measurement method, CSM, [4]. This last technique consists in adding small oscillations (as part of this work, 5nm) while charging at a high frequency (45 Hz). The contact stiffness is measured by the response of displacement at the excitation frequency. This technique evaluates the modulus and stiffness versus depth of penetration, the mechanical properties are deduced when they have reached a plateau value after a penetration of about 200 nm. We must keep in mind that during the first oscillation behavior of local plasticity under the indenter is not reached. Once the local plasticity is reached, the elastic response upon unloading leads to an estimate of the relevant mechanical properties of the material tested, resulting in reaching a plateau value [5].

3 Results and discussions

3.1 Microstructural analysis

Before measuring the mechanical properties, the use of confocal microscopy allows the visualization of surfaces, exposed or not, and provides information on the structure and damage caused by UV radiation. Fig. 3 highlights the difference between exposed and unexposed surface roughnesses. The center of the sample was exposed to UV radiation while the outline was protected. Roughness, RMS (roughness mean square) calculated on a surface of 164 microns x 164 microns, is about 0.1 microns for the unexposed areas, 0.8 microns and 1.2 microns respectively for 2 and exposed surfaces 4 weeks. For comparison, Rosu et al. presented samples of vinyl around the same emission spectrum and at the same temperature but the flow is received twice as large (300 W / m^2) and has also noticed that the index variation of brightness of the micrographs show increased roughness after 200 h of irradiation, while the non-irradiated sample has a smooth surface [9].

The evolution of the surface showed singularities around the mineral additive particles. Indeed, one can notice that after irradiation, the matrix leaves apparent additives and fibers that remain intact (Fig. 4). The height of the intact fibers and the matrix is negligible for an unexposed surface of the order of 5

microns for a sample exposed 2 weeks and 10 microns for a sample exposed 4 weeks. These observations were made on areas of high, medium and low fiber density and on the vinylester monolithic, assessing the height between the additive particles and the matrix. The results are of the same magnitude. This means that the contraction and/or removal of the matrix is independent of fiber density. Two hypotheses can be envisaged. First, the removal increases with the duration of exposure and can therefore be assumed that the material is removed by ablation result of UV radiation. It may be confirmed or invalidated by exposing samples to longer durations. This work is currently underway. The second case involves a form of structural rearrangement of the matrix, followed by a contraction, following exposure to UV-temperature. An appropriate structural study is currently ongoing.

3.2 Direct indentation on exposed surfaces

Keeping in mind that the depth of indentation is of the same order of magnitude as the roughness of the exposed surfaces, a first study on indentation allows direct comparison of the properties obtained with similar materials previously studied. The first part of Tab. 2 shows the numerical results of tests on the vinylester order of magnitude of results is comparable with previous studies of Signor on the vinylester nanoindentation, exposed to UV radiation which gets values between 1.23 and 3.7 GPa [10]. We can then note that the standard deviations of results for samples exposed (Table 2, in bold) are far from negligible and does not provide evidence on the evolution of mechanical properties of the material. Indeed, some assumptions are not valid in our case, especially because the surface has a roughness that inevitably creates deviations from the assumption of hydrostatic applied stress. In addition, the vinylester studied contains mineral additives. To circumvent this problem, it is possible to identify each of the indentations on the interaction of an additive or not using the LSCM. It should be noted that the indentations made directly on the additives are not considered in these results. However the problem of roughness can be directly bypassed because it is impossible to remove it for the reasons summarized above.

On the vinylester matrix in a composite material exposed to UV radiation, the mechanical properties evaluated from indentations are twice as large as the

monolithic vinylester. This increase can be explained by the effects of surrounding fibers that interact with the strain stress field following the indentation. This result can also be compared with the results of Goel who noted that the evolution of Young's modulus in the exposed regions of polypropylene (PP) is greater in the composite than in the monolithic PP presentation [11]. He assumed that mineral additives are accelerating damage occurrence within UV-exposed matrix.

3.3 Indentation on cross section

The first idea was to plot statistical distribution by increasing indentation number. This statistical analysis gave Gauss distribution [12] but not accurate enough and needed a lot of data. The second solution is to cut it across the sample in vinyl, the coat of epoxy and polish on its cross section, in order to indent on a row across the sample thickness (Fig. 5). This method is directly inspired by the work of Forster [13], whose row indentation allows the characterization of a multilayer coating. Thus, in our case, polishing can be seen on the edge, while not destroying the irradiated layer. In addition, this method also helps to know the depth of the impact of UV radiation.

Two types of tests were carried out: the samples are placed at an angle of about 10 ° and 20 ° between the exposed surface and the row of indentations. On the 10° angle, 60 indentations (about 30% in epoxy and 70% in the vinyl) were performed every 15µm. On the 20° angle, 50 indentations were carried out every 40 microns. In the first case (Fig. 6), wherein the thickness and the distance between each indentation was relatively small, a continuous behavior was recorded which enabled to determine the existence or absence of edge effects. In the second case (Fig. 7), where the thickness portion is larger, the evolution of mechanical properties through the thickness, including evaluating the layer affected by UV irradiation, can be allowed.

Regarding the unexposed vinylester matrix, in the 2 cases listed above, the mechanical properties are almost constant. Thus, we can assume that the material is homogeneous and edge effects are negligible. The latter assumption is well implemented on the samples exposed. Near the sample surface (for low values of abscissa), the longer is the exposure, the higher are the mechanical properties. The results decrease with

depth in the sample to move towards levels corresponding to the characteristics of unexposed vinylester. This allows the estimate of the layer affected by UV radiation at 500. Beyond this limit, the material does not appear to be modified. Goel made the same conclusions with the analysis of the evolution of Young's modulus, a sample of polypropylene (PP), exposed to UV radiation [13]. Without taking into account the decrease of mechanical properties, we can observe that the standard deviation of the results of nanoindentation on cross-sectional area is much smaller than results we got when testing directly on the steep surface. Nevertheless, there are still differences on result, especially when considering indentations in the surrounding of mineral additives. Even if the indentation is not directly carried out on the additive, the area under the indentation is influenced as shown on Fig. 8.

Conclusions

The images obtained by confocal microscopy enables us to notice the contraction of the matrix with respect to additives and fibers that remain intact. Further experiments, increasing the exposure time, would define whether ablation of the material or structural alteration of the matrix. These studies are in progress. The very large deviations of the results obtained from indentations performed directly on the exposed surface are due to the roughness caused by the degradation due to UV irradiation. This is why direct indentation on such surfaces cannot be productive. In such case, the deviation is simply reflecting the scatter to hydrostatic loading conditions that must prevail when performing indentation tests. The proposed solution is therefore to cut the sample transversely, to polish it and make a row of indentations across the depth. The dispersion of results is much lower and allows us to conclude that this method is much more reliable. The results show that the local Young's modulus and hardness are affected to a thickness of 0.5 mm and that these mechanical properties increase with the duration of exposure.

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	Direct indentation on exposed surfaces		Indentation on cross section	
	Mean	St. Dev.	Mean	St. Dev.
0 week	4.58	0.66	3.84	0.35
2 weeks	4.40	2.39	4.36	0.37
4 weeks	4.39	1.52	4.65	0.48

	Direct indentation on exposed surfaces		Indentation on cross section	
	Mean	St. Dev.	Mean	St. Dev.
0 week	0.231	0.011	0.189	0.014
2 weeks	0.123	0.119	0.209	0.027
4 weeks	0.132	0.091	0.232	0.030

Tab.1. Mean values and standard deviation (St. dev.) of modulus (a) and hardness (b) estimated by nanoindentation testing on neat vinylester samples using CSM Method and Berkovich tip.

Fig.1. Load vs. displacement performed on polished unexposed monolithic and composite samples.

Fig.2. Indentation on epoxy resin at 1000 nm with a Berkovich tip.

Fig.3. 2D and 3D unexposed and 2 weeks exposed micrography (1.64mm x 1.64 mm). The center of the sample was exposed to UV radiation while the outline was protected.

Fig.5. Successive zooms of indentation row – schema and LSCM micrographs.

Fig.4. Downward, 3D unexposed, 2 and 4 weeks exposed vinyl ester-glass fiber composite micrography.

Fig.6. Local modulus (a) and hardness (b) versus the distance between indent and vinyl ester edge for unexposed and 4 weeks exposed sample, Berkovich tip with a 1000 nm depth, using CSM Method. Linear interpolation for the trendline.

Fig.7. Local modulus (a) and hardness (b) versus the distance between indent and vinyl ester edge for unexposed, 2 weeks and 4 weeks exposed sample, Berkovich tip with a 750 nm and 1000 nm, using CSM Method. Polynomiale interpolation for the trendline.

Fig.8. Indentation on neat surface but with an interaction between the plastic zone and filler.

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